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Research Article

**ASSESSMENT OF PATIENT SATISFACTION LEVELS ON
HOSPITAL SERVICES AMONG IN AND OUT PATIENTS IN
A TERTIARY CARE SETTINGS –A PROSPECTIVE STUDY****Pooja^{1*}, Dr.Sushma Muchukota¹, KarishmaParveen², Rashi.L³,
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Sai Krishna⁸, Mohan K B⁹, Dr. Rinkumathappan¹⁰.**¹Pharm.D(Ph.D), Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmacy Practice, Gautham College of Pharmacy, Bangalore, Karnataka, India.^{1*-9}III Pharm.D (students), Department of Pharmacy Practice, Gautham College of Pharmacy, Bangalore, Karnataka, India.**Abstract:**

Background: Patient satisfaction defined as degree of congruency between a patient's expectations of ideal care and his/her perception of the real care they receive. Representing a essential marker for quality of healthcare delivery and an accepted factor which needs to be studied repeatedly for smooth functioning of health care systems .

Aim & Objectives: The aim of the study was to access the patient satisfaction levels for the services offered in a tertiary health care setup among both in patient and out patient .The study was conducted by discussing 12 structured questionnaires amongst 243 patients to find out factors which satisfy them and assist in finding solutions to upgrade the quality of services provided .

Methods: It is a Hospital based, Prospective, Cross-sectional and Observational study with sample sizes of (N = 243) and both in and out patients are considered into study. The patients were interviewed and data was collected and analysed in figures , tables and percentages. The questions were related to demographic and overall service process in both out patients and in patients.

Results: The study reveals that Out of 243 patients considered for the study majority of them were males from rural background of the age group 40-49 years i.e., 103(42.38%).Of them i.e 110 (45.26%) were overall satisfied with the services they received .

With 121 (49.79%) patients satisfied with cleanliness of the hospital , 42% of them rated doctor _ patient relationship as excellent ,55.14% of them were satisfied with behaviour of physician and 41(16.8 %) of them dissatisfied with the pharmacists .

Conclusion: This study concluded The patients were highly satisfied with their doctors and we're ready to revisit the hospital .it recommended that further studies should be conducted to assess patient satisfaction in the primary and secondary health facilities and efforts should be made to get regular feedback from the patients .The majority satisfies were with respect to cleanliness and with conduct of physician , whilst the minor dissatisfies with respect to the pharmacists .

Keywords: Structured questionnaires, Prospective, Cross-sectional, Observational studies, Patient satisfaction.

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INTRODUCTION:

Patient satisfaction is a virtual phenomenon has led to the substitution of the idea of 'quantity of life' by a more patient centered concept of 'quality of life'^[1]. It is defined as the measure of congruency in connecting a patient's expectations of ideal care and his /her opinion of the real care what they actually receives^[2]. It necessary key marker and symbol for the quality of health care delivery and desires to be repeatedly studied for easy functioning of the health care systems^[3]. In the past, we used to estimate the quality of medical services by evaluating the objective outcomes of patient's physical condition. Recently researchers have begun to pay close attention to patients' satisfaction as a measure for assessing the effectiveness and quality of medical care.^[4] As a result of the expanding importance of patient's satisfaction, a variety of measurement tools are developed and tested. The satisfaction questionnaire being the majority effective, widely used methods and other like Suggestion boxes, formal complaints, qualitative methods, audits, and satisfaction questionnaires are being used to assess the level of patients' satisfaction^[5]. These determinants may be either provider-related or patient-related. A number of provider-related factors like physician's proficiency, interpersonal communication skills, behavior of hospital staff, access to care, basic facilities, and also infrastructure. Patient-related factors include sociodemographic characteristics of patients, stage of their disease as well as patients' perception of a relationship of trust and feeling of being involved in decisions about their care^[6,7,8]. A recent study showed that there is no significant association between patient satisfaction and quality of care^[9]. Patient satisfaction surveys are often not followed by changes in medical provider behaviour or hospital care^[10]. Measuring patient satisfaction was also criticized for not discriminating between hospitals^[11,12,13]. These surveys should be able to put satisfaction ratings into perspective rather than having them for their own individual hospital only^[14]. Many previous studies have developed and applied patient satisfaction as a quality improvement tool for health care providers. Thus, patient satisfaction is an important issue both for evaluation and improvement of healthcare services^[15].

Aim and Objectives

The aim of the study was to assess the patient satisfaction levels on hospital services among in and outpatients in a tertiary care settings.

METHODOLOGY:

Study sample: The sample size collected for our study is [N=243 Patients visiting ESI hospital]

Study Design: It is A Hospital-based, Prospective, cross-sectional and observational study.

Study Period: The present study was conducted for a period of 6 months from September 2019 to February 2020.

Study site: The present study was conducted in ESI Hospital, Indira Nagar, Bangalore.

Study Criteria:

Inclusion criteria: All patients between age group of 15 to 85 years attending the outpatient department (OPD) and admitted in various specialties of indoor patient departments (IPD) visiting ESI hospital and who are willing to participate in the study were included. Thus, a total of 243 patients of ESI hospital were enrolled for the study.

Exclusion criteria:

The patients who are not willing to participate in the study and the patients admitted to the intensive care unit/cardiac care unit/emergency with conditions related to psychiatry, maternity and those with severe acute or chronic illness were excluded from the study.

Source of Data:**Method of collection of data:**

All the patients satisfying the inclusion criteria were selected after explaining the study to the subjects then included in the study. Tool of data collection Structured interviewing questionnaire was designed to collect data.

Statistical tools: Data were collected from the patient direct face to face interview and was subjected to analyze by performing descriptive statistics. The obtained data tabulated and analysed in terms of objectives of the study, by using inferential and descriptive statistics.

RESULTS:**Table 1 : Socio-demographic profile of the respondents (n= 243)**

S.NO	DEMOGRAPHIC DETAILS	NUMBER		TOTAL NO(%)
		MALE	FEMALE	
1	AGE			
	<20yrs	8	7	15(6.1%)
	20-29yrs	22	3	25(10.28%)
	30-39yrs	38	22	60(24.6%)
	40-49yrs	63	40	103(42.38%)
>50yrs	42	8	50(20.57%)	
2	EDUCATION			
	Literate	50	19	69(28.3)
	Illiterate	101	52	153(62.9%)
	Others	12	9	21(9.4%)
3	OCCUPATION			
	Employed	55	27	82(56.7%)
	Unemployed	95	43	138(56.7)
	Others	13	10	23(9.4%)
4	FAMILY INCOME			
	1-3 lakhs per annum	93	53	146(60%)
	3-5 lakhs per annum	46	17	63(25.9%)
	>5 lakhs per annum	24	10	34(13.9%)
5	PLACE OF RESIDENCE			
	Rural	99	50	149(61.3%)
	Urban	57	21	78(32%)
	Others	7	9	16(6.5%)

Table 2 : Patient satisfaction questionnaire in the study conducted in ESI hospital Indira Nagar^[16,17,18].

Questions	Excellent	Very good	Good	Poor
1.How satisfied are you with the effect of your {treatment/care}?	20(8.23%)	100(41.15%)	120(49.38%)	3(1.23%)
2.How satisfied are you with the explanations given you about the results of your {treatment/care}?	35(14.40%)	90(37.03%)	110(45.26%)	8(3.29%)
3.The {doctor/other health professional} was very careful to check everything when examining you	29(11.93%)	80(32.92%)	130(53.49%)	4(1.64%)
4. How satisfied were you with the choices you the doctor/other health professional has in decisions affecting your health care? given you about treatment/care?	42(17.28%)	95(39.09%)	100(41.15%)	6(2.46%)
5. How much of the time did you feel respected by the doctor/other health professional?	25(10.28%)	101(41.56%)	115(47.32%)	2(0.82%)
6. Are you satisfied with the care you received in the hospital/clinic?	19(7.81%)	98(40.32%)	125(51.44%)	1(0.41%)
7. How was the confidentiality maintained by the doctors?	32(13.16%)	89(36.62%)	119(48.97%)	3(1.23%)
8. How doctors explained about the side effects of medication?	14(5.76%)	99(40.74%)	128(52.67%)	2(0.82%)
9. How doctors provided instructions regarding dose and time of	35(14.40%)	100(41.15%)	105(43.20%)	3(1.23%)

medications?				
10. How clean was the hospital?	19(7.81%)	101(41.56%)	121(49.79%)	2(0.82%)
11. How was hospital diet service?	24(9.87%)	99(40.74%)	119(48.97%)	1(0.41%)
12. Overall how would you rate the care you received	28(11.52%)	100(41.15%)	110(45.26%)	5(2.05%)

Fig.No.1: Patient Satisfaction questionnaire.

Fig.No.2: Patient satisfaction questionnaire

Table 3: Patient satisfaction with the attitude and behaviour of the healthcare providers^[17].

Aspect of care	Satisfied		Dissatisfied	
	Inpatient (n=169)	Outpatient (n=74)	Inpatient (n=169)	Outpatient (n=74)
Behaviour of Physician	98	36	65	36
Nurse	30	12	45	21
Pharmacist	26	16	31	10
Others	15	10	28	7

Fig.No.3: Behaviour of health care providers.**Table 4: Patients satisfaction to healthcare services^[17].**

PATIENT OVERALL RATING					
ASPECT OF CARE	Excellent	Very good	Good	Fair	Poor
Doctor-patient relationship	42	25	20	11	2
Availability of general basic facilities	51	24	16	15	4
Information and support	40	35	10	14	1
Accessibility to health care services	12	33	46	6	3
Organization of care	49	22	20	7	2

Fig.No.4: Patient overall rating.

DISCUSSION:

The overall study was to assess the patient satisfaction levels on hospital services among in and outpatients in a tertiary care settings.^[19] This study assess the level of satisfaction of patients, who visited the hospital were satisfied with doctor and it was observed that 55.14% of patients who visited the hospital were satisfied with doctor. Contrary results were obtained from a study carried out in Scotland where only 52% of patients were reasonably satisfied with their doctors^[20]. Patients' views on various aspects of doctor-patient interaction were ascertained. 120(48.38%) of patients found that they are satisfied with the effect of treatment/care. 125(51.43%) of patients were satisfied with the explanations given to them about the results of their treatment/care. 216(88.88%) of patients felt respected by the doctor/other health professional. This is comparable to other international studies which reported that 88–92% of their patients believed that they were treated with respect and dignity^[21,22]. 117(48.13%) patients were satisfied with the care you received in the hospital/clinic. 121(49.78%) patients were satisfied with in the confidentiality maintained by the doctors. According to a study carried out in Karachi 62.4% of the patients agreed that the doctor maintained privacy^[23]. 205(84.35%) patients were satisfied with the instructions provided by the doctors regarding dose and time of medications. 113(46.50%) patients were of the view that doctors didn't enlighten the side effects of medication. Patients were asked about hospital cleanliness, 120(49.37%) patients were satisfied with the cleanliness of the hospital. In a study conducted by University of North Carolina at

Charlotte, patient cleanliness of the facility was also high (mean score of 1.70 out of 2)^[24] In our study, 121(49.78%) patient were satisfied with confidentiality maintained by doctors. In a study conducted by PIMS Institute, Islamabad. Patient satisfaction with waiting time, accessibility of services, confidentiality and cleanliness of the facility was only 54%^[25]. 123(50.61%) patients were satisfied with the hospital diet service. The overall satisfaction of patients with services received from this tertiary care institute came out to be, satisfied (79.83%) and dissatisfied (20.16%) which is similar to the figures reported by SA Deva et al.^[26] in Kashmir (80%), Kumari et al.^[27] in luck now, (81.6%) and Qureshi et al.^[28] in Kashmir (72%) whereas it is lower than as reported by Bhattacharya et al (88%)^[29], SK Jawhar et al.^[30] in India (90-95%) and colleagues (83%)^[31] in Benin city but higher than those reported from Mahapatra et al in Andhra Pradesh (63%)^[32].

CONCLUSION:

Patients provided ratings relating to the care, respect, explanations regarding dose, time of medications, side effects, behaviour of health care providers and patient satisfaction to healthcare services. This study concludes that the patients are highly satisfied with their doctor and ready to revisit the hospital. It is recommended that further studies should be conducted to assess patient satisfaction in the primary and secondary health care facilities and effort should be done to get regular feedback from the patients. The majority satisfies were with respect to cleanliness and with conduct of physician, while the minor dissatisfies were with respect to the pharmacists.

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